

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF MICROFINANCE TRAINING & DEVELOPMENT AND PROBLEMS OF LOAN ON WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

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Abstract -The research tries to discover the impact of microfinance training & development and problems of loan on women entrepreneurs. Descriptive research design was chosen for this research. The sample size of the research is considered to be 50 small business women entrepreneurs through snowball sampling technique in Villupuram district. Therefore, it is concluded that there is impact of microfinance training on women empowerment and performance of women entrepreneurs. It is also identified that there is no impact of problems of loan on women empowerment and performance of women entrepreneurs. Finally, the research discovered that there is influence of women empowerment on performance of women entrepreneurs. Hence, it is recommended that microfinance institutions should reduce interest rates on loans to small business women entrepreneurs and change the way small business women entrepreneurs repay loans. This will make it easier for small business women to get loans from them to run their businesses without considering them as profit-making enterprises.

Key Words: Microfinance training, Problems of Microfinance Loan, Women Empowerment and Performance of Women Entrepreneurs.

INTRODUCTION

Smith and Reece (1999) stated that the business performance as the operational capability to meet the needs of small business entrepreneurs. Also, it is an assessment to quantify the achievements of a small business entrepreneur. Since the role of microfinance is an independent variable, in business performance, the dependent variable constitutes the 'women empowerment'. Similarly, the role of microfinance in business performance has very important consequences. If the potential effects are positive they lead to the development of small business entrepreneurs. Otherwise, the small business enterprise may suffer. Business performance can lead to improved revenue, business economics, business expansion, profit margin, infrastructure, increased revenue, increased equity, horizontal growth of the company and overall assets. These factors of a company can make a difference in the growth rate of the company. The growth of small business enterprises is usually measured by management and its cash

flow. Thus the role of microfinance affects small business performance to the extent of microcredit.

The study is intended to discover the microfinance on women empowerment in Villupuram district. The dependent variables are women empowerment, business performance among women entrepreneurs. The independent variable is microfinance such as training and loan problem. This study is conducted only for small business women entrepreneurs located in Villupuram district.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sazzad Parwez & Ruchi Patel (2022) found that the microcredit program has reduced social inequalities to some extent and empowered women. The research suggested that microcredit has failed to promote the socio-economic transformation needed by the community.

Fawzeya Ahmed Abdelhameed & Yasmin Ahmed Sakr (2022) identified that microfinance is a significant determinant of asset ownership. In other words, improving women's financial inclusion through microcredit is critical to improving equity, sustaining economic growth and reducing poverty.

Mohamed AbdallahAli, MazharMughal & DinaChhorn (2021) discovered that there is positive association between microcredit and women's empowerment. The research also discovered that Households with access to loans from MFIs are economically (35.4%), socially (30.9%) and interpersonally (10.1%) empowered. The analysis also discovered that the number of loans and access to microfinance was significant. Finally, the research revealed that positive socioeconomic effects of microfinance programs.

Bui Thanh (2021) had investigated the impact of microfinance on women empowerment. The research discovered that there is negative impact of microfinance services on women empowerment. Similarly, research has found that women can become empowered when they work together for long periods of time in a women's union.

Prathiba & Shanmugasundaram (2021) identified that women business performance was influenced by role of microfinance such as microfinance training & development, microfinance savings and microfinance loan.

Bui Thanh (2021) examined the impact of microfinance on women empowerment. The author discovered that there is negative influence of microfinance services on women empowerment. Conversely, this research assumed that women can become empowered if they join a women's association for a long time.

Patel, et al. (2018) identified that microcredit services reduce the level of poverty and increase the quality of life of poor women. The research provided perspectives on microfinance and women's empowerment.

Rahman, et al. (2017) identified that microcredit services have a positive impact on most of the selected indicators of women's empowerment. This research has provided an approach to assess the impact of microfinance on women's empowerment.

Kanimozhi and Natarajan (2017) discovered that there is no relationship between dimensions of functions of microfinance like support of microfinance loan and problems of microfinance loan with growth of small business enterprises. It is discovered that there is no influence of dimensions of functions of microfinance like support of microfinance loan and problems of microfinance loan on effects of microfinance and also growth of small business enterprises.

Velaudham and Baskar (2017) found that there is influence of training & motivation and financial support on social recognition. The study highlighted that there is influence of social recognition on rural women empowerment. Hence, it is suggested that SHG has a profound influence on the economic status, decision making power, knowledge and self worthiness of rural women participants of self help group linkage program in Dharmapuri district. It is concluded that SHG is playing a vital role in the social, psychological as well as economic empowerment of rural women in Dharmapuri district. SHG loan avaiement and its productive utilization found to be having a profound role and impact on rural women empowerment.

Al-Shami, et al. (2016; 2017) identified that microcredit improved gender equality and women's empowerment. Also, microcredit helps women create micro and small businesses, access financial capital, and generate the income women need to contribute to household expenses.

RESEARCH GAP

There has been a lot of research done on the microfinance and women empowerment worldwide, but very few researches has been done in the Indian context. Similarly, impact of microfinance training & development and problems of loan on women entrepreneurs has not been addressed in Villupuram district.

FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The findings of this study will help women entrepreneurs and policy makers. This study will help identify the impact of microfinance training & development and problems of loan on women entrepreneurs. Findings from this study can help women entrepreneurs to increase their performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The microfinance plays an important role in empowering small business women entrepreneurs in many countries. The problems faced by small women entrepreneurs arise from various levels. Many women entrepreneurs find themselves improving through economic empowerment, social empowerment, political empowerment, psychological empowerment, business empowerment, personality empowerment, managerial empowerment and gender awareness index. Microfinance institutions have been implementing strategies aimed at proving solutions to the sustainability challenges affecting women entrepreneurs to grow.

OBJECTIVES

- To discover the impact of microfinance training & development and problems of loan on women empowerment.
- To find out the impact of women empowerment on performance of women entrepreneurs.

HYPOTHESES

- There is impact of microfinance training & development and problems of loan on women empowerment.
- There is no impact of women empowerment on performance of women entrepreneurs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to explore the impact of microfinance on women empowerment a descriptive research design is employed by the researcher. Data is collected district through a structured questionnaire. This descriptive research design is employed to explore the relationship between microfinance training & development and problems of loan, women empowerment and performance of women entrepreneurs.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

Data is collected from women entrepreneurs Villupuram district through a well-designed questionnaire. The questionnaire construction for this study is divided into four parts. The first part of the questionnaire is arranged in such a way to know the demographics profile of the women entrepreneurs, the second part microfinance, the third part is women empowerment and the fourth part is performance of

women entrepreneurs. Except first part, all the four sections are constructed with multiple choice questions. The first part is set up as a category and the other three as a measuring scaling technique.

Table 1: Questionnaire Construction

S.No.	Variable	Items	Author
I	Demographic Profile	12	----
II	Role of Microfinance	10	Developed by the Researcher
	Training	5	
	Problems of Loan	5	
III	Women Empowerment	32	
IV	Performance of women entrepreneurs	8	

RELIABILITY

Pilot study was done to confirm that the results of this study questionnaire are reliable. The questionnaires are verified by involving 50 women entrepreneurs in Villupuram district. Based on the women entrepreneurs’ opinion, some changes are made in the questionnaire as suggested by the women entrepreneurs. Cronbach’s alpha tool is employed to test the reliability of the research variables. All the variables of this questionnaire are above 0.70 which shows that it is reliable. This means that the set of questionnaire has a high reliability value.

Table 2: Reliability of the research

S.No.	Variable	Items	Reliability
I	Role of Microfinance	10	0.85
	Training	5	0.88
	Problems of Loan	5	0.89
II	Women Empowerment	32	0.88
III	Performance of women entrepreneurs	8	0.90

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

In this study, snowball sampling technique has been applied to collect the primary data from women entrepreneurs in Villupuram district. In these ways 50 women entrepreneurs are approached to collect the primary data in Villupuram district.

STATISTICAL TOOLS

Path analysis is used to estimate model by probing the relationship between microfinance, women empowerment and performance of women entrepreneurs. The researcher has employed the path analysis to identify the impact of microfinance training & development and problems of loan on women entrepreneurs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 3 presents the mode summary of impact of digital technology on BSNL employees’ behaviour. The path model presented, along with mode summary to verify the model fitness. The Chi-square statistic is 1.205 with $p > 0.05$. The table illustrates the model fit statistics such as RMSEA, RMR, NFI, CFI, AGFI and GFI. RMR and RMSEA are within than the recommended limit i.e., RMR and RMSEA is less than 0.08 (Indra, Balaji and Velaudham, 2020; Velaudham and Baskar, 2016). NFI, CFI, AGFI and GFI are within than the recommended limit i.e., NFI, CFI, AGFI and GFI is greater than 0.90 (Kantiah Alias Deepak and Velaudham, 2019; Velaudham and Baskar, 2015). All the model fit statistics imply a better model fit (Premapriya, et al. 2016; Victor and Velaudham, 2020).

Figure 2: Impact of microfinance training & development and problems of loan on women entrepreneurs

Table 3: Model Fit Indication

S.No.	Model Fit Indicators	Calculated Values in the Analysis	Recommended Values (Premapriya, et al. 2016)
1	Chi-Square	1.205	---
2	p	0.272	> 0.050
3	GFI	0.957	> 0.90
4	AGFI	0.996	

5	CFI	0.999	< 0.080
6	NFI	0.993	
7	RMR	0.017	
8	RMSEA	0.038	

Source: Primary data

Table 4: Regression Weights

DV	IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	p
Women Empowerment	<--- Training & Development	0.439	0.050	8.846	0.625	0.001
Women Empowerment	<--- Problems of Microfinance Loan	0.074	0.067	1.100	0.078	0.271
Performance of Women Entrepreneurs	<--- Women Empowerment	0.679	0.159	4.272	0.384	0.001
Performance of Women Entrepreneurs	<--- Training & Development	0.326	0.127	2.570	0.161	0.010
Performance of Women Entrepreneurs	<--- Problems of Microfinance Loan	0.200	0.116	1.718	0.072	0.086

Source: primary data

H₁: Training & development significantly influences women empowerment.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrates that the C.R. value is 8.846; β value is 0.625 and p value is significant. The result revealed that training & development influences women empowerment at 62.5%. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrates that the training & development significantly influences women empowerment. The result of the research is similar to the findings of Fawzeya Ahmed Abdelhameed & Yasmin Ahmed Sakr (2022) which is also identified that microfinance is a significant determinant of asset ownership.

H₂: Problems of microfinance loan significantly influences women empowerment.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrates that the C.R. value is 1.100; β value is 0.078 and p value is not significant. The result revealed that problems of microfinance loan not influences women empowerment at 7.8%. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrates that the problems of microfinance loan not influences women empowerment. The result of the research is similar to the findings of Bui Thanh (2021) which is also discovered that there is negative impact of microfinance services on women empowerment.

H₃: Training & development significantly influences performance of women entrepreneurs.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrates that the C.R. value is 2.570; β value is 0.161 and p value is significant. The result revealed that training & development influences performance of women entrepreneurs at 16.1%. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrates that the training & development significantly influences performance of women entrepreneurs. Prathiba & Shanmugasundaram (2021) identified that women business performance was influenced by microfinance training.

H₄: Problems of microfinance loan significantly influences performance of women entrepreneurs.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrates that the C.R. value is 1.718; β value is 0.072 and p value is not significant. The result revealed that problems of microfinance loan not influences performance of women entrepreneurs at 7.2%. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrates that the problems of microfinance loan not influences performance of women entrepreneurs. Kanimozhi and Natarajan (2017) discovered that there is no relationship between dimensions of functions of microfinance like support of microfinance loan and problems of microfinance loan with growth of small business enterprises.

H₁: Women empowerment significantly influences performance of women entrepreneurs.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrates that the C.R. value is 4.272; β value is 0.384 and p value is significant. The result revealed that women empowerment influences performance of women entrepreneurs at 38.4%. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrates that the women empowerment significantly influences performance of women entrepreneurs. Prathiba & Shanmugasundaram (2021) identified that women business performance was influenced by role of microfinance such as microfinance training & development, microfinance savings and microfinance loan.

FINDINGS

The research discovered that the training & development significantly influences women empowerment. The result of the research is similar to the findings of Fawzeya Ahmed Abdelhameed & Yasmin Ahmed Sakr (2022) which is also identified that microfinance is a significant determinant of asset ownership.

It is found that the problems of microfinance loan not influences women empowerment. The result of the research is similar to the findings of Bui Thanh (2021) which is also discovered that there is negative impact of microfinance services on women empowerment.

The analysis identified that the training & development significantly influences performance of women entrepreneurs. Prathiba & Shanmugasundaram (2021) identified that women

business performance was influenced by microfinance training.

It is revealed that the problems of microfinance loan not influences performance of women entrepreneurs. Kanimozhi and Natarajan (2017) discovered that there is no relationship between dimensions of functions of microfinance like support of microfinance loan and problems of microfinance loan with growth of small business enterprises.

The analysis found that the women empowerment significantly influences performance of women entrepreneurs. Prathiba & Shanmugasundaram (2021) identified that women business performance was influenced by role of microfinance such as microfinance training & development, microfinance savings and microfinance loan.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Microfinance institutions should reduce interest rates on loans to small business women entrepreneurs and change the way small business women entrepreneurs repay loans. This will make it easier for small business women to get loans from them to run their businesses without considering them as profit-making enterprises.

It is recommended that microfinance institutions improve the socio-economic empowerment of small business women entrepreneurs by providing reasonable amounts of credit and easily accessible.

It is recommended that women entrepreneurs join business skills training programs offered by microfinance institutions to enhance their business empowerment to achieve their business growth and broaden their business acumen.

CONCLUSIONS

Microfinance can increase economic power and women's mobility through increased consumption. Access to microfinance services helps women improve their roles in their families by making purchases for family needs. The changes that women bring about in their families will lead to changes in society. Descriptive research design was chosen for this research. The sample size of the research is considered to be 50 small business women entrepreneurs through snowball sampling technique in Villupuram district. Therefore, it is concluded that there is impact of microfinance training on women empowerment and performance of women entrepreneurs. It is also identified that there is no impact of problems of loan on women empowerment and performance of women entrepreneurs. Finally, the research discovered that there is influence of women empowerment on performance of women entrepreneurs. Hence, it is recommended that microfinance institutions should reduce interest rates on loans to small business women entrepreneurs and change the way small business women entrepreneurs repay loans. This will make it easier for small business women to get loans from

them to run their businesses without considering them as profit-making enterprises.

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The heading should be treated as a 3rd level heading and should not be assigned a number.

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